

Annotation. The main projection for architectural drawings is the plan of the building. The plan of the building is called the plan of the clipped building, which is characterized by a horizontal plane passing slightly above the window. **Keywords:** Architecture, Drawing, projection, building, plan, window, horizontal, plane.

Drawing-technical science, which includes drawings of objects (various machines, mechanisms, buildings, structures, etc.), krunkridas and methods for drawing schemes, maps and graphs, making images of various objects; dealing with drawing drawings, projects. The basis of drawing is geometry, drawing is the science of geometry. The task is to learn how to draw images, projects and sketches of various objects using drawing tools, read drawing drawings, make axonometry. The content and size of the drawing is anicized depending on what area of Science and technology it is intended for. Sections of drawing science: geometric drawing; projection drawing; machine drawing, construction drawing and other geometric drawing will study drawing tools, drawing drawings, geometric making, junctions and curved drawings. P in the projection drawing, points, a straight line, flat shapes, making images of geometric bodies and issues related to their mutual situation, axonometric images and other are seen. In Mechanical Engineering Drawing, the types of drawings, views, cuts, cuts, rhombuses and other, and in construction drawing, conditional signs of parts of a building, sanitary equipment items, as well as drawings of buildings and structures are studied. Those who are engaged in drawing drawings (schemes, maps and graphs) are called draftsmen. Engineers, Constructors and designers from various fields are required to know drawing.

The construction drawings obtained as a result of the measurement of the finished construction object are called execution drawings. In the case of the construction of such drawings, deviations from the loyikha are made for the purposes of expropriation or capital repair of the building, or when it is necessary to build a new floor over an existing building.

The procedure for drawing up sketching drawings of buildings is approximately the procedure for drawing up sketches of machine-building details. Measure using roulette with two or even three workers bajariladi.to ' the face of non-rectangular rooms is measured first after dividing them into triangles. The thickness of the walls is measured in window positions or taken from the subtraction of the external and internal dimensions. The thickness of the covers is determined by measuring the external dimensions between the window openings. Height dimensions are laid out in the form of an otmet. Otmetka is said to indicate how much height is in meters or centimeters from the first floor zero SATX, for example, from any SATX taken to zero. Postcards are written on the drawing next to the icon in the form of a triangle

The second type of construction drawings. With loyikha drawings

you will have to do more. On the basis of the task of the building, drawings of the technical project are developed they are usually; 1) general Plan of the construction site, 2) plan of the building 3) facades 4) trimmings 5) perspective drawing of the building. After the confirmation of the work, the work drawings of the work on the basis of the drawings of the technique are processed. Their composition includes the following. 1) identified general plan 2) plans of the building in which various uskins are located 3) sections of the building 4) drawings of certain structures (stropolia farms zina, etc.) 5) details of certain construction rings 6) drawings of different uskins (vodoprod channeling heating mechanical equipment)

The main projection for architectural drawings is the plan of the building. The plan of the building is called the plan of the clipped building, which is characterized by a horizontal plane passing slightly above the window octi SATX. The amount of plans is mold to the size of the building floor. From them, the plan of the foundation to another project is attached to the plan for the placement of beams in the enclosures: the plan of the stropyas and the plan of the roof. The vertical view of the buildings is called the facade of general views without trim. Facades can be a facade with a side facade pile of several head facades. To determine the internal structure of the building, longitudinal and transverse shears are used. Clippings should, as a rule, pass along the axes of the window and door positions. When cutting staircase rooms, the cutting plane must pass through one of the marches. The cut marsh is strung on a drawing or painted in a dream

In the construction projects of modern times, dividing axes with symmetrical axes of walls and columns of lifting structures are often placed on the plan and shearing of buildings. The dividing axes are drawn with barricaded lines and graduated with circles with a diameter of 8-10 mm. Vertical axes with numbers horizontal axes are denoted by harfs. For large industrial buildings, the distance between the transverse axes is taken so that the step of the columns is equal to 6m. the distance between the longitudinal axes is equal to the numbers divisible by 3 (6 9 12 15 m and hokazo

Scaling in construction drawing, the following scales are used. Location Plan 1:500, 1:10000; general Plan of the plot 1:500, 1: 000; plans of buildings 1:100, 1:200, 1:400; cuts and facades 1:100, 1:200; details of the main structures 1:20, 1:50; details of the parts responsible for aloxida 1:5, 1:10; schemes 1:50 or 1:200. As the presented scales show, the construction is done with drawings almost on small scales. Only the details of the parts responsible for aloxida are performed on scales that are common in mechanical engineering drawing the use of different scales for the plan and shearing of large buildings can be reduced by the difference in the scale sizes indicated above.

Literature

1. Odilbekovich, S. K., & Islomovna, M. F. (2023). Technology of Work on the Replacement of Contaminated Ballast below the Sole of Sleepers. *New Scientific Trends and Challenges*, 1, 21-24.
2. Odilbekovich, S. K., & Islomovna, M. F. (2023, January). Facilities and Devices of the Yale Farm. In *Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences* (pp. 21-23).
3. Самандаров, X. O. (2023). Образование Выплесков В Пути. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 144-147.
4. MAMUROVA, FERUZA ISLOMOVNA. "FACTORS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE CONTEXT OF INFORMATION EDUCATION." *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука* 9 (2021): 538-541.
5. Mamurova, F., & Yuldashev, J. (2020). METHODS OF FORMING STUDENTS'INTELLECTUAL CAPACITY. *Экономика и социум*, (4), 66-68.
6. Islomovna, M. F., Islom, M., & Absolomovich, K. X. (2023). Projections of a Straight Line, the Actual Size of the Segment and the Angles of its Inclination to the Planes of Projections. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 140-143.
7. Mamurova, F. I. (2022, December). IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS AND BUILDERS. In *INTERNATIONAL*

SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 97-101).

8. Islomovna, M. F. (2022). Success in Mastering the Subjects of Future Professional Competence. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(5), 224-226.

9. МАМУРОВА, Ф. КОМПЕТЕНТЛИ ЁНДАШУВ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛУВЧИНИНГ КАСБИЙ СИФАТЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. *PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT*, 152.

10. Shaumarov, S., Kandakhorov, S., & Mamurova, F. (2022, June). Optimization of the effect of absolute humidity on the thermal properties of non-autoclaved aerated concrete based on industrial waste. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2432, No. 1, p. 030086). AIP Publishing LLC.

11. Pirmazarov, G. F., Mamurova, F. I., & Mamurova, D. I. (2022). Calculation of Flat Ram by the Method of Displacement. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(4), 35-39.

12. Kadirova, E. (2021, March). USING OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN INFORMATICS LESSONS. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 28-33).